

RELATIONS BETWEEN PROPERTIES OF WETTING AND IMPREGNATION, TECHNOLOGY, AND APPLICATION OF FRP

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For laminates of high quality as used for printed circuit boards a complete connection between the glass fibre reinforcement and the polymer is required. This is necessary to prevent destructive influences of liquid mediums which can occur when defects in micro-areas are existing.

The phenomenon of wetting the reinforcement by the polymer is here very important. In this connection we shall report about investigations of wetting resp. contacting of glass fabrics with the polymer. Differently finished fabrics are used here.

Furtheron we investigated the prepregs with regard to their quality of impregnation. We shall emphasize the phenomenon of "capillary-lines" which are based on the existence of microcavities. We recognized that they are not caused by bad wetting but by hindering the wetting as a result of gummings between the filaments by coupling-agents and of the fabric structure.

We shall point out the filling of the microcavities with polymer during the impregnation as a key-problem of the prepreg process because of the tendency of using coarser fabrics, higher working-speed, and other requirements.

Finally we shall report about our experiences in contacting fabrics with polymer to achieve a high quality of impregnation with regard to the capillary-lines and microcavities mentioned above.

O. INTRODUCTION

Plane fibre glass-polymer-laminates are produced by a hot-pressure-process using prepregs as well known. This process is appropriated for obtaining laminates of high quality, especially for electrical insulation materials, and among others to manufacture epoxy resin glass fabric laminates for printed circuit boards.

This paper is classified as follows:

- 1) Let us begin with some basic questions of prepreg-forming.
- 2) Observing a prepreg in detail you can see typical appearances which differ from an ideal compound between the reinforcement and the polymer.
- 3) We will attempt to characterize the morphology of prepregs, representing the reasons for compound defects in prepregs, and to describe the effects on the secondary processing and the properties of material.
- 4) Last but not least we will show technological possibilities to produce prepregs of a higher quality of impregnation.

1. SOME BASIC QUESTIONS OF PREPREG-FORMING

The prepreg-forming bases on a number of material conditions which must be converted in the properties of the prepregs during processing as shown in Fig. 1.

When we regard the polymer there are physico-chemical conditions like properties of sorption, surface-tension, viscosity, and time of polymer-B-stage of the polymer-mixture. Besides the viscosity depends on the temperature of the mixture in the basin.

The B-stage-time of a mixture or a prepreg is that time which is required for curing the polymer. A special heating plate containing calottes is used for this test. The temperature is controlled and we operate at 150 degrees Celsius for mixtures and at 170 C for prepregs. The test samples from the prepregs are obtained by wrinkling whereby resin is abraded.

As to the glass-reinforcements we have to consider the pick-up of polymer and the wetting of filament yarns. The compatibility between polymer and reinforcement within the interface between glass and resin is influenced by the structure of the fabrics and their surface-treatment (finish).

If an equipment is already existing there is a handicap with regard to the type of dryer-box, its dimension, and to the level of temperature and its profile during the drying process. In such a case it is important to realize the weight of prepreg M_p and the B-stage-time of the prepreg B_{Tp} which are the main targets of this process.

To achieve these targets by the vertical dryer-box technology there are mainly two functions with parameters to characterize the prepreg-forming process which we try to show in Fig. 2.

Fig. 1: Basic conditions and targets of prepreg-forming process

These two functions are

- (1) the weight of prepreg M_p as a function of the working-speed v with the flow-behaviour, esp. the viscosity η as a parameter, and
- (2) the B-stage-time of prepreg Bt_p also as a function of the working-speed v and with the temperature of the dryer-box as a parameter.

At first we start with the target "weight of prepreg M_p ", in Fig. 2 called Z(1), and - when choosing a certain viscosity - we achieve a working-speed v .

Then we start with the target "B-stage-time of prepreg Bt_p ", called Z(2), and we can choose the temperature to achieve the same value of the working-speed. You see that this method is an iterative one.

But we must say that this problem is not so simple as plotted in this figure. In fact the system of predetermining the targets is a very complicated one because there are further influences by the fabric and by the polymer - as mentioned in this figure on the left - and because nowadays all these correlations can only be determined empirically.

Fig. 2: Schematic diagram showing the behaviour of contacting a fabric with polymer to form a prepreg
 Target Z(1): Weight of prepreg M_p
 Target Z(2): B-stage-time of prepreg Bt_p

However we only have considered one side of the composite-formation namely the "behaviour of application" to achieve the characteristic values of the prepreps as required. These - the weight and the B-stage-time - are basic values of the following pressure process which are characterized by the reactivity and flow. This behaviour must be converted with regard to the programs for temperature and time and for pressure and time to achieve certain contents of polymer resp. reinforcement in the final product.

2. DEFECTS IN PREPREGS

Besides the behaviour of application a second category of quality which we like to term "quality of impregnation" belongs to the composite-forming. This term characterizes the impregnation in so far as the polymer is applied homogeneously to and into the textile reinforcement, without any defects inside and outside, and whether the surface of the prepreg is plane and the thickness uniform.

To achieve a high quality of impregnation it is necessary to reach a complete connection between polymer and reinforcement which is also important in micro-areas. It is necessary to get such an extremely good connection because of dimensioning the material [1, 2] and to prevent a penetration of liquid mediums into the interior of the laminate [3, 4].

Again and again experience has proved that we nowadays are still lacking to have a high quality of impregnation. Let us emphasize three defective phenomena in prepregs. We have to note that besides these there are other kinds of defects like dirt, ruptures, holes, smashes, and so on. But this paper does not deal with such defects.

Fig. 3 shows surface defects which are characterized by exposed reinforcement. The result is an uneven thickness of the prepreg in micro-areas, called "weave texture" or "weave exposure" [5]. On the left you see the top view, and on the right a drawing of a polished section of a laminate. This defect mostly happens when too low a polymer-content was intended or realized.

Fig. 3: Bad quality of surface

left: top view on a prepreg

right: drawing of a cross section through a laminate

Fig. 4: Pinholes in a prepreg (left) and in a laminate (right)

Fig. 4 shows pinholes in a prepreg, a defect mostly caused when drying is too quick. If the B-stage-time is low this defect cannot be completely eliminated by the following press-process.

Now let us investigate in detail the prepreg-defect "capillary-lines" because there are not yet any descriptions about this phenomenon, its causes and effects. Besides a perfect prepreg Fig. 5 gives you by means of drawings an idea of prepregs with capillary-lines of different intensity. To characterize the intensity we introduced marks:

- mark 0 for "not resp. hardly to be seen"
- mark 1 for "slightly to be seen"
- mark 2 for "much to be seen"
- mark 3 for "very much to be seen".

Fig. 5: Schematical drawing of prepregs with "capillary-lines" to give an idea for judging their intensity (mark 0 to 3)
 (The prepreg shown in Fig. 4 left has got about mark 2 and you can see that in this case the intensity of capillary-lines is higher for the warp than for the weft)

Fig. 6: Polished sections of prepregs containing capillary-lines: hollow spaces between filaments are to be seen (arrows).
 Magnification: left 75 : 1 , right 150 : 1

The capillary-lines are to be seen by little magnification and they run in axial direction within the filament yarns of warp and weft. This appearance is originated by microcavities in the interface between reinforcement and polymer. Their diameter is about 5 to 50 micrometers and their length is limited. We ascertained that capillary-lines are hollow spaces between the filaments which are not filled up with polymer, distinctly to be seen by Fig. 6.

3. ABOUT CAUSES AND EFFECTS OF CAPILLARY-LINES IN PREPREGS

We refer to the applicability of HAGEN-POISSEULE's law and its preparation by ZVONAR [6]. For this reason the filling up of a capillary system with liquids is, converted to the impregnating process,

- directly depending on the surface-tension, on the cosine of the contact-angle, and on the time of contacting, and it is further
- indirectly depending on the viscosity of the polymer-mixture and the thickness of the reinforcement material.

We should like to show the effect of these factors by means of examples. Our starting-point are epoxy resin-systems, containing solvents, catalysts, and accelerators, and glass filament fabrics which are partly varied to their textile construction and to their surface-treatment.

- As to the WETTING-PROPERTIES

Fig. 7 shows the results of physico-chemical investigations of the surface [7]. At first we look at the head of this figure which represents the surface-energy of glass filament yarns γ_s for different surface-treatments. In spite of having different surface-energies we recognize that - compared with the surface-tension of the epoxy resin-system γ_F - a basic condition for a total wetting is satisfied: γ_s is larger than γ_F .

At the bottom of this picture the corresponding cosine of contact-angles are plotted which show the contact-angle of 0° for untreated glass filaments. For modified silane-finish and for epoxy-silane angles of about 15° and for aminosilane of about 30° were tested. Basing on this investigations we assumed a different wetting.

By means of a light-beam transmission method [8, 9] you can state that this is correct and that means the treatments are arranged in the same sequence as with the measurement of the contact-angles as shown in Fig. 8. Worst results were obtained for aminosilane and in comparison with it best results for the condition without surface-treatment (thermically desized).

We judged the quality of impregnation, expressed in marks for the appearance of capillary-lines as mentioned above, at a constant viscosity and at a constant contacting time. The results were mark 0 to 1 (that is "not to slightly to be seen") at best wetting (for thermically desized), mark 1 (that is "slightly to be seen") with unimportant worse wetting (for modified silane-finish and epoxy-silane), and mark 2 (that is "much to be seen") with obvious worse wetting (for aminosilane).

Fig. 7: Surface-energy γ_s and contact-angles $\cos \phi$ for different surface-treatments of the glass filament yarn

- | | |
|------------------------------|---|
| MSF - Modified silane-finish | C-A - Coupling-agent |
| ES - Epoxysilane | MCK - Methacrylic acid chromium complex |
| MS - Methacrylsilane | |
| AS - Aminosilane | |

Note to Fig. 4 right: We have drawn the pinholes in black for better copying.

Fig. 8: Behaviour of wetting glass fabrics with different surface-treatments by epoxy resin - light-beam transmission method

MSF - Modified silane-finish MS - Methacrylsilane
ES - Epoxysilane AS - Aminosilane

With these results we conclude: There is a correlation between the quality of impregnation and the behaviour of wetting caused by the surface-treatment of the glass filament. The better the behaviour of wetting the better the quality of impregnation.

- As to the VISCOSITY (see Fig. 9)

Fig. 9: Influence of polymer viscosity η on the quality of impregnation (expressed by marks) for different surface-treatments

In this diagram we have plotted the quality of impregnation as a function of the polymer viscosity with different surface-treatments of the glass filament fabrics. The fabric type and the time of contact remained constant. We conclude that the quality of impregnation shows a slight downward tendency if the viscosity of the polymer increases. But this influence is relatively small within the range of viscosity up to 100 Ford-seconds which is conventionally applied with processing.

- As to the TIME OF CONTACTING (see Fig. 10)

In this diagram you see the quality of impregnation as a function of the contacting time with different surface-treatments. We kept the viscosity of polymer and the type of fabric constant. In this way we get to know that the quality of impregnation can be improved by prolonging the contacting time.

Regarding the impregnation process you can substitute the contacting time by the quotient of dip-length which is given technologically and by the working-speed. Consequently you can obtain a better quality of impregnation by decreasing the working-speed or by prolonging the dip-length in the construction.

Fig. 10: Influence of the time of contacting t_K on the quality of im pregnation (by marks) for different surface-treatments of the fabric

- As to the WEIGHT OF FABRIC (see Fig. 11)

Fig. 11: Influence of the weight of fabric M_F on the wetting with epoxy resin and on the quality of impregnation (by marks)

In the Fig. 11 we have plotted the wetting time that was tested light-colorimetrically as a function of the fabric thickness. The weight of the analogous fabric ranges from 50 up to 235 g/m². The treatment and the viscosity remained constant. Moreover we registered the marks for the quality of impregnation. Please notice that with increasing weight of the fabrics their thickness increases as well in which case thicker threads and higher yarn densities are usually needed. You can see that the coarser the fabric the worse the quality of impregnation.

The knowledge gained by studying a "capillary-system" to be filled with liquids was confirmed by contacting of fabrics during the prepreg process. We received a better quality of impregnation by realizing better wetting by higher surface-energy of the glass reinforcement and by lower surface-tension of the polymer, and by using an increased contacting time and lower fabric weight. The influence of the viscosity on the quality of impregnation was not so remarkable if we consider the range of viscosity which is used in practice nowadays.

How is it possible that microcavities are existing within a fabric? How are they caused and how do they effect the capillary-lines? These are the questions we will deal with in the following. Please regard Fig. 12.

Fig. 12: Formation of microcavities in a filament yarn of a fabric
left: caused by the finish
(gummed spots between the filaments)
right: caused by the fabric structure
(packing density of the filaments)

There are two causes which hinder the transport of polymer into the fabric:

- (1) Gummings of filament yarns by the coupling-agent are typical for finished fabrics. The coupling-agent not only covers the filaments but there are many gummed spots between the filaments. This principle is shown on the left drawing of Fig. 12.
- (2) The coarser the filament yarn the more filaments must be packed and in this way the volumina of air in a thread increases. The package of the filaments is physically limited by the "most compact package of cylinders". For this reason a bigger volume of air must be displaced by the polymer during the impregnating process. In this way the possibility of forming capillary-lines increases. Please look at the drawing on the right. Thus we can say that the higher the density of filaments the more difficult the problem of displacing the air by polymer during the contacting process.

Let us summarize that the formation of capillary-lines is not simply caused by "bad wetting" of the reinforcement by polymer. If wetting properties are principally existing the formation of microcavities during contacting is caused by the density of package of filaments and moreover by partial gummings between the filaments by coupling-agents.

You can oppose that the microcavities are filled with polymer by forced flowing during the press process. But you cannot expect this effect in general. Special tests showed that the following factors remain or get critical:

- . high glass-contents,
- . pressure-bags with altogether a low quality of impregnation,
- . coincidence of weave exposure with low quality of impregnation,
- . demands for a low flow-out rate of resin that are preferred to prevent resin-starved board-edges and excessive expulsion of foam,
- . avoidance of extremely high pressure to exclude "twist" of the cured boards,
- . deviations of the press-program with regard to the temporal control of temperature and pressure corresponding to the behaviour of viscosity as a function of time depending on temperature and on the behaviour of flow and curing of the polymer.

Furtheron we have to consider that in the diagram of closing the press as a function of time there is a phenomenon if pre-pregs of a low quality of impregnation are pressed which we call "gas-step". This gas-step is registered after the cold-flow and before beginning the hot-flow: The compressing of the pressure-bags is stopped for some minutes and an "expansion" occurs because the air - or more generally the gas - in the microcavities and in the pinholes expands. This effect is an undesired deviation compared with the ideal behaviour.

We can show that prepregs with a low quality of impregnation result in "resin-starved lines" in a cured laminate if several causes mentioned above coincide. In the polished section as shown in Fig. 13 you see black areas marked by arrows proving the absence of polymer between several filaments.

Fig. 13: Polished section of a laminate showing "resin-starved lines" - There is not any polymer between the filaments (see arrows)

4. TECHNOLOGICAL POSSIBILITIES TO IMPROVE THE QUALITY OF IMPREGNATION

When summarizing some main directions of development in the field of prepregs you can recognize the following tendencies

- (1) Coarser glass fabrics i.e. higher weights are increasingly preferred because they can be produced and converted economically.
- (2) With regard to a higher productivity higher working-speeds with prepreg-units are required.
- (3) There is a tendency to use mixtures of polymer with low or without solvents. These mixtures must be converted with higher viscosities. The cause for this tendency is in the field of ecology and economics. The same effect of increasing the viscosity occurs when using filler-additives which are also necessary for the application of certain reinforcements, f.i. for non-woven fabrics, with regard to their processing.

All these factors influence the quality of impregnation negatively. For this reason we have to start with the contacting of the polymer to achieve a higher quality of impregnation. In this way we take care of the tendencies of development as mentioned above.

Machine builders and technologists discussed or partly realized different ways [11, 12, 13, 14] to improve the quality of impregnation:

- Steps to remove layers of sorption of the reinforcement material as drying by heat or by freezing;
- steps to increase the surface-energy of the reinforcement material by electrostatic treatment and by activations with electric discharge when gaseous substances are present;
- steps to decrease the surface-tension of polymer by addition of certain solvents and surfactans;
- processes to support the transport of polymer into and through the capillary-system, as f.i. by supplying kinetic energy with mechanical vibrators and ultrasonics, or by arranging several and larger impregnating basins, by using multiple impregnations - with so-called "breathing-steps" -, roll-, dip- and overroll cylinders, pull-off, and vakuüm systems.

To improve the quality of impregnation we proceeded from the phenomena mentioned above and have constructed a device to solve this problem as shown in Fig. 14.

Fig. 14: Technological variety of contacting a fabric with polymer to improve the quality of impregnation

By the mode of origin of capillary-lines we concluded that air must be replaced by polymer during the process of contacting. By using simple tip-impregnation this process requires a lot of time: more than 10 minutes according to Fig. 11. The reason for this is that the microcavities are immediately and completely enclosed with polymer. Replacing the air by polymer is a process dependent on time.

For this reason we tested several systems to precontact the reinforcement with polymer, and the polymer-applicating roll proved favorable, see Fig. 14. The primary contact is made in such a way that the polymer impregnates the fabric from one side only. So the

air has got an opportunity to escape to the other side, that is the side opposite to the primary contacting. Thus the processing operates in such a way that the threads are not immediately and not completely enclosed with polymer.

However we must take care that any predrying up to the next phase of contacting does not occur. The next phase is a so-called "impregnation storage" which causes to massage the polymer into the fabric and to prolong the time of contacting as well.

In the third phase the fabric dips into the impregnating basin to get the weight of prepreg as required.

By such a multiple contacting system we have been able to improve the quality of impregnation up to mark 0 to 1 compared with the conventional simple dip-impregnating which resulted in mark 2 and 2 to 3 for the same reinforcement material.

With this paper we have intended to emphasize causes and effects of defects in prepregs which occur in micro-areas and we have treated the quality of impregnation which is a problem for polymer-technologists. We have pointed out the improvement of the quality of prepregs esp. to produce basic materials for printed circuit boards as a key-problem for further development of the prepreg process.

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